

EFFECT OF *AZADIRACHTA INDICA* EXTRACTS ON POST-HARVEST FUNGI ASSOCIATED WITH YAM (*DIOSCOREA ROTUNDATA* POIR.) ROT IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Yam (*Dioscorea rotundata* Poir.) is a vital staple food and cash crop in Nigeria, but post-harvest losses due to yam rot pose significant threats to food security and economic stability in the region. This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of *Azadirachta indica* extracts in controlling post-harvest fungi associated with yam rot in the study area. A total of 40 yam tubers, including both rotten and healthy samples, were collected from farms and markets. Additionally, one kilogram of *Azadirachta indica* leaves was obtained from the Botanical Garden of the Plant Science Department at Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria. Three fungal species; *Fusarium solani*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Aspergillus flavus* were isolated from the rotten yam tubers. Among these, *A. niger* was identified as the most pathogenic, followed by *A. flavus*, while *F. solani* exhibited the least virulence. The aqueous extract of *A. indica* demonstrated significant ($P < 0.05$) inhibitory effects on the growth of all three fungi at various concentrations (25%, 50%, 75%, and 100%) compared to the control. Phytochemical analysis of *A. indica* revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, polyphenols, tannins, and steroids, while glycosides and coumarins were absent. The extract concentrations of 50%, 75%, and 100% showed strong antimicrobial activity against the test fungi, indicating the potential of *A. indica* as a natural antifungal agent for managing post-harvest yam rot.

Keywords: Yam, Postharvest Rot, *Azadirachta indica*

INTRODUCTION

Yam (*Dioscorea rotundata* Poir.), a key staple crop belonging to the Dioscoreaceae family, is widely cultivated across Africa, Asia, Latin America, the Caribbean, and Oceania. It produces edible underground tubers that play a crucial role in food security, medicine, and economic development, particularly in developing countries (Ita *et al.*, 2020; Obidiegwu *et al.*, 2020). In 2021, global yam production reached 75 million tonnes, primarily in the "yam belt" of West Africa, where Nigeria, Benin, Ghana, and Côte d'Ivoire account for over 90% of production (FAO, 2022). Among these, the white Guinea yam (*Dioscorea rotundata*) is the most cultivated and preferred variety (Iseki & Matsumoto, 2020). Nigeria is the world's largest producer, contributing around 65% of global production, followed by Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire (FAO, 2018). In Nigeria, Taraba State is a significant yam-producing region, contributing over 13% of the country's total production (Sodiq, 2023), with around 60% of the produce sold locally or exported (Asiedu and Sort, 2010).

However, the production of white Guinea yam faces numerous challenges, including biotic and abiotic factors that reduce yields and cause loss of varietal diversity (Gwa *et al.*, 2021). Despite high output, yam tubers are vulnerable to various pathogens, including bacteria, fungi, nematodes, and viruses (Okigbo *et al.*, 2015; Gwa & Richard, 2018; Gwa & Okrikata, 2019). Fungal pathogens, in particular, are a major cause of rot in yam tubers both in the field and during storage (Nweke, 2015). A study by Gwa and Ekefan (2021) found that fungal infections caused rot in stored yam tubers, with infection rates between 6.67% and 13.33% after five months of storage.

Traditional storage methods, which rely on room temperature, are inadequate for controlling decay, leading farmers to either consume or sell their produce at low prices before the new harvest season. This creates a risk of food insecurity before the next harvest. Although chemical agents have been used to prevent post-harvest losses, they are costly, harmful to the environment, and ineffective over time due to the development of microbial resistance (Okigbo *et al.*, 2015).

Recent studies suggest that plant-based bioactive substances from species such as *Azadirachta indica*, *Carica papaya*, *Piper guineense*, *Zingibe officinale*, and *Nicotiana tabacum* can effectively inhibit the growth of fungi responsible for yam rot. These natural substances are safer, more affordable, and environmentally friendly alternatives to chemical agents (Gwa and Richard, 2018). In view of the above, the aim of this research is to determine the effect of neem leave extract in the control of postharvest fungi associated with the rotten of yam in zing and Yorro local government areas of Taraba state, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Large quantity of yam losses has been reported and these losses have been due to microbial rot diseases. Yam tuber is prone to infection by fungi, bacteria, and viruses at all stages of growth and also during storage of tubers which aligns with studies by Gwa and Richard (2018), Gwa and Okrikata (2019). Difficulties in yam preservation has compelled majority of the yam farmers to either consume or sell all their yam products at low prices before the new harvesting season. Consequently, before new harvesting period, they are bound to suffer food security crises. Chemical agents have been used to control this pre harvest and post-harvest losses in the past decades but these chemical agents are not only expensive for farmers, but they are not ecofriendly and micro-organisms are becoming resistant to them which aligns with findings from Okigbo *et al.*, (2015). The post-harvest period for yam in Zing and Yorro Local Government Areas of Taraba State presents a significant challenge due to the prevalence of fungi causing rot. One primary issue revolves around the identification of these fungi responsible for the deterioration of yam tubers was the lack of comprehensive knowledge on the specific fungi involved, hampers the development of effective control measures.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the efficacy of *Azadirachta indica* extracts in controlling post-harvest fungi associated with yam rot in Zing and Yorro Local government areas of Taraba State, Nigeria with the following specific objectives;

- i. to isolate and identify fungi responsible for post-harvest rot of yam tubers in Zing and Yorro Local government areas of Taraba State, Nigeria.
- ii. to evaluate the effects of aqueous extracts of *Azadirachta indica* on post-harvest spoilage of yam in Zing and Yorro Local government areas of Taraba State, Nigeria.

- iii. to evaluate the phytochemical constituents of the plant extracts.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided this study:

- i. What is the fungi responsible for post-harvest rot of yam tubers in Zing and Yorro Local government areas of Taraba State, Nigeria?
- ii. What are the effects of aqueous extracts of *Azadirachta indica* on post-harvest spoilage of yam in Zing and Yorro Local government areas of Taraba State, Nigeria?
- iii. What is the phytochemical constituents of the plant extracts?

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The study was conducted in Zing and Yorro Local Government Areas of Taraba State, Nigeria. It has a tropical wet and dry savannah climate, with an average yearly temperature of 31.14°C (88.05°F), which is 1.68% higher than the national average. Zing receives about 103.37 mm (4.07 inches) of precipitation annually, with over 151 rainy days (41.44% of the year). Yorro, on the other hand, experiences a slightly cooler average temperature of 29°C and an estimated average wind speed of 10 km/h. Yorro is located at Latitude 8° 43' 11" N and Longitude 11° 37' 8" E.

Collection of Sample Materials

A total of 40 yam tubers, including both healthy ones and those showing signs of rot, were surveyed from farms and markets in the study area. Ten tubers were selected and transported to the Plant Science Department laboratory at Modibbo Adama University, Yola, located at latitude 9° 22' 00" N and longitude 12° 33' 00" E. Additionally, 1 kg of *Azadirachta indica* leaves was collected from the university's Botanical Garden.

Preparation of Growth Medium

To prepare the growth medium, 39 grams of Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) was mixed with 1 liter of sterile distilled water and autoclaved at 121°C for 15 minutes. After cooling, 250 mg of the broad-spectrum antibiotic Chloramphenicol was added to 500 ml of the molten PDA. The mixture was gently shaken to ensure uniformity before being poured into 9 cm Petri dishes.

Isolation and Identification of Fungal Pathogens

Fungal pathogens were isolated using the method of Okigbo *et al.* (2015). Yam tubers showing rot symptoms were washed with tap water, surface sterilized with sodium hypochlorite for 30 seconds, and rinsed with sterile distilled water. Small pieces of the tubers with visible rot were then inoculated onto solidified Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) plates. The plates were sealed and incubated at 25°C for 3-5 days, with daily observations for fungal growth. Pure cultures were obtained by sub-culturing on fresh PDA and incubating for 7 days. Fungal identification was done by examining the structures under a microscope, using a hand lens for preliminary observations, followed by slide mounting and staining with cotton blue lacto-phenol. Identification was based on the features described in Barnett and Hunter (1987). A pathogenicity test was carried out

in triplicate, and the severity of the infection was measured in millimeters using a meter rule. The mean percentage infection (disease severity) was calculated using the formula from Umana *et al.* (2015).

Study Design

A Completely Randomized Design (CRD) was used for the study. The experiments were replicated three times, with five different treatments. In total, 45 Petri dishes were used, with 15 dishes per replicate. The various fungal isolates served as the different treatments.

Preparation of Plant Leaf Extracts

Fresh neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaves were thoroughly washed with tap water, rinsed with sterile distilled water, air-dried, and then ground into a fine powder using a mortar and pestle. Following the serial dilution method outlined by Gupta and Kumar (2016), different concentrations of the neem leaf extract were prepared by infusing 25g, 50g, 75g, and 100g of the powdered leaves in 100 mL of sterile distilled water in 500 mL conical flasks. The mixtures were stirred with a sterile glass rod, left to infuse for 24 hours, and then filtered through a four-fold cheesecloth into fresh flasks. These extracts corresponded to 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% concentrations of aqueous neem leaf extract.

In Vitro Screening of Plant Extracts against Radial Fungal Growth

The effect of plant extracts on mycelial growth of three test fungi was assessed using the food poisoning technique (Gwa & Nwankiti, 2018). Two milliliters of each plant extract concentration (25%, 50%, 75%, and 100%) were mixed with 9 mL of molten PDA and evenly spread in Petri dishes. After solidifying, the plates were inoculated at the center with a 5 mm mycelial plug from 7-day-old fungal cultures. The plates were incubated at 25°C for 5 days and then examined for growth inhibition. Colony growth was measured along two perpendicular lines, and the percentage inhibition was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Percentage inhibition} = \frac{(R1-R2)}{R2} \times 100$$

Where R1 is the radial growth in the control plate and R2 is the radial growth in the extract-treated plates

Qualitative Phytochemicals Analysis of *Azadirachta indica* Leaf Extract

The qualitative phytochemical analysis of *Azadirachta indica* (neem) leaf extract was conducted using standard protocols. The presence of various compounds was tested through the following methods:

1. **Alkaloids:** Mayer's and Wagner's tests were used to detect alkaloids. A green precipitate (Mayer's) or a brick-red precipitate (Wagner's) indicated their presence.
2. **Flavonoids:** The alkaline reagent test and Shinoda test were performed. The appearance of an intense yellow color, which became colorless after adding dilute HCl, confirmed the presence of flavonoids. A pink color after adding hydrochloric acid and magnesium also indicated flavonoids.
3. **Saponins:** The foam test was used, where the formation of a foam layer in the solution signaled the presence of saponins.
4. **Terpenoids:** Chloroform extract, when treated with concentrated sulfuric acid, showed a reddish-brown color at the interface, indicating the presence of terpenoids.

5. **Glycosides:** Salkowski's and Keller-Kiliani tests were used. The appearance of a reddish-brown color (Salkowski's test) or a brown ring (Keller-Kiliani test) suggested the presence of glycosides, specifically steroidal or cardiac glycosides.
6. **Polyphenols and Tannins:** The addition of FeCl₃ solution to the extract produced a blue-green or blue-black coloration, confirming the presence of polyphenols and tannins.
7. **Steroids:** Two tests for steroids were performed. In the first, a red coloration in the chloroform layer after adding sulfuric acid indicated steroids. In the second, a greenish color formation after adding both sulfuric and acetic acids suggested the presence of steroids.
8. **Coumarins:** The extract residue was dissolved in hot water, and after cooling, treated with ammonium hydroxide. The presence of fluorescence indicated coumarins.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27. Mean values were compared using Duncan's multiple range test at a 0.05 significance level to determine any significant differences between the values.

RESULTS

Fungal Organisms Isolated from Yam Rot

The morphological and microscopic characteristics of fungal isolates from yam exhibiting rot symptoms are summarized in Table 1 and Plate 1. The three fungi studied displayed distinct growth textures: *A. niger* had a dense, powdery texture filled with conidiophores, *A. flavus* had a rough texture, and *F. solani* exhibited a smooth texture. In terms of surface color: *A. niger* started white or yellow, quickly turning black; *A. flavus* appeared greenish-yellow and woolly; and *F. solani* formed off-white, cottony colonies. The reverse side colors varied: *A. niger* changed from white to pale, *A. flavus* turned from cream to yellow, and *F. solani* had a pale yellow color.

Pathogenicity Test

A pathogenicity test was conducted on three fungal isolates: *Fusarium solani*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Aspergillus flavus*. All three fungi caused rot in healthy yam tubers within seven days of inoculation. *Aspergillus niger* was the most virulent, causing a rot incidence of 100 mm and a pathogenicity of 28 %. It was followed by *Fusarium solani*, which caused a rot incidence of 70 mm and had a pathogenicity of 20 %. The least virulent was *Aspergillus flavus*, with a rot incidence of 60 mm and a pathogenicity of 17 %.

Effects of Aqueous Extracts of *Azadirachta indica* on the Inhibition of Test Organisms

The effects of *Azadirachta indica* leaf extract on the inhibition of test fungi were evaluated at 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% concentrations. At 25% concentration, the growth of *Fusarium solani* was the lowest (76%), followed by *Aspergillus flavus* (72.67%), and *Aspergillus niger* showed the least growth (8.33%). At 50% concentration, *F. solani* was again the lowest (75.67%), followed by *A. flavus* (55.67%) and *A. niger* (48.67%). At 75% concentration, *F. solani* was completely inhibited (100%), followed by *A. niger* (65.33%), while *A. flavus* showed the least inhibition (59.67%). Finally, at 100% concentration,

both *F. solani* and *A. niger* were fully inhibited (100%), while *A. flavus* was inhibited by 95.33%. In all cases, the control group showed no inhibition (0.00%).

Phytochemical Analysis of *Azadirachta indica*

The phytochemical analysis of *Azadirachta indica* revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, polyphenols, tannins, and steroids. However, glycosides and coumarins were not detected in the sample.

Table 1: Morphological and Microscopic Features of Fungal Isolates from Yam Rot

S/N	Species of fungi	Morphological features			Microscopic features
		Texture of growth	Colour of surface	Colour on reverse	
1.	<i>Aspergillusniger</i>	Powdery, dense, filled of conidiospores	White to yellow which quickly turns to black	Turns from white to pale	The hyphae are septate and clear with long conidiophore and unbranching.
2.	<i>Aspergillusflavus</i>	Rough texture	Greenish yellow colour and looks wooly	Cream to yellow	Has septate hyphae with long conidiophore and branching.
3.	<i>Fusariumsolani</i>	Smooth texture	Off-white cottony colonies	Pale yellow	The hyphae are clear and non-pigmented and are septate. The conidiophores are short

Plate I: Surface Pure Culture of *A. niger*

Plate II: Reverse Pure Culture of *A. niger*

Plate IV: Surface Pure Culture of *A. flavus*

Plate V: Reverse Pure Culture of *A. flavus*

Plate III: Surface Pure Culture of *Fusarium solani*

Plate III: Reverse Pure Culture of *Fusarium solani*

Figure 2: Pathogenicity test of *A. niger*

Figure 3: Pathogenicity test of *A. flavus*

Figure 1: Morphological characteristics of the fungi isolates

Table 2: Pathogenicity Test of Isolates on Healthy Yam Tubers

Fungal species	AE (mm)	TA (mm)	Pathogenicity (%)
<i>A. flavus</i>	60	350	17
<i>A. niger</i>	100	350	28
<i>F. solani</i>	70	350	20

Key: AE- Area of Effect, TA-Total Area

Table 3: Effects of aqueous leave extract of *Azadirachta indica* on the inhibition of 7 days after inoculation of Fungal Pathogens

CE	Fungal species (%)	Inhibition (%)
0	<i>A. flavus</i>	0.00 ±0.0 ^a
	<i>A. niger</i>	0.00 ±0.0 ^a
	<i>F. solani</i>	0.00 ±0.0 ^a
25	<i>A. flavus</i>	72.67±2.31 ^b
	<i>A. niger</i>	8.33±4.16 ^c
	<i>F. solani</i>	76.00±6.00 ^a
50	<i>A. flavus</i>	55.67±4.04 ^b
	<i>A. niger</i>	48.67±5.03 ^c
	<i>F. solani</i>	75.67±21.36 ^a
75	<i>A. flavus</i>	59.67±3.51 ^{ab}
	<i>A. niger</i>	65.33±9.71 ^b
	<i>F. solani</i>	100.00±0.00 ^a
100	<i>A. flavus</i>	95.33±8.08 ^{ab}
	<i>A. niger</i>	100.00±0.00 ^a
	<i>F. solani</i>	100.00±0.00 ^a
P-value		0.00**

Key: CE-Concentration of Extract, **- highly significant, means with different superscripts are significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$)

Table 4: Qualitative phytochemical screening of *A. indica* leaves extract

Phytochemicals	Leaves
Alkaloids	+
Flavonoids	+
Saponins	+
Terpenoids	+
Glycosides	-
Polyphenols and tannins	+
Steroids	+
Coumarins	-

Key: (+) = presence, (-) = absence

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Fungal Organisms Isolated from Yam Rot

In this study, three fungal species; *Fusarium solani*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Aspergillus flavus* were identified from rotting yam tubers. These fungi are commonly found on yam due to factors such as improper handling, poor storage conditions, high humidity, temperature fluctuations, and contaminated environments. *F. solani* is typically found in soil and infects yam tubers through wounds or natural openings. It thrives in moist conditions and grows best at temperatures between 20-30°C, utilizing the starch and other nutrients in yam for growth. *Aspergillus flavus* spores are widespread in the air and can enter the tubers through wounds or natural openings. It can grow in dry conditions, making it a frequent contaminant in stored yams. *A. flavus* grows at temperatures ranging from 12-45°C and utilizes starch and proteins in the yam. Similarly, *A. niger*, also commonly found in soil, can infect yam tubers through wounds during post-harvest handling. It prefers a growth temperature range of 20-40°C and similarly feeds on the yam's starch and proteins. The fungal species found in this study are consistent with previous reports, including *A. flavus*, *A. niger*, *Rhizopus* spp., *Fusarium* spp., *Sclerotia rolfsii*, and *Rhizoctonia* spp., which were also isolated from cocoyam. These findings aligned with research by Adjebeng-Danquah *et al.* (2021), which identified various fungi, including *A. flavus*, *A. niger*, and *F. solani*, as major contributors to yam tuber rot. This study also corroborates Shiriki (2019), who isolated *Rhizopus stolonifer*, *A. niger*, *A. flavus*, and *F. solani* from rotting yam tubers and demonstrated high inhibition of these fungi using *Azadirachta indica* extracts.

Pathogenic fungi organisms from yam rot

In the study, *Aspergillus niger* was identified as the most pathogenic fungus responsible for yam rot, followed by *Aspergillus flavus*. The least virulent fungus was *Fusarium solani*. This finding aligns with previous research by Okigboet *et al.* (2015), which also found these fungi to be pathogenic on *Dioscorea rotundata* in Awka, Anambra State. The pathogenicity test confirmed that *A. niger*, *A. flavus*, and *F. solani* caused rot in white yam tubers, with *A. niger* being the most virulent.

This supports Gwaet *al.* (2018), who reported that *A. niger* acts as a secondary pathogen in rotten white yam tubers after pathogenicity tests were conducted.

Effects of Aqueous Extracts of *Azadirachta indica* on the inhibition of Test Organisms

The study investigated the antifungal effects of *Azadirachta indica* (neem) aqueous extracts on three fungal pathogens; *Fusarium solani*, *Aspergillus flavus*, and *Aspergillus niger* which are responsible for yam rot. The neem extract effectively suppressed the growth of these pathogens, with the highest inhibition correspond with highest concentration of the extracts. This outcome aligns with previous research by Aji and Tunwari (2018), which identified *Aspergillusniger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, and *Rhizopus stolonifer* as common pathogens on *Dioscorea rotundata*.

The antifungal activity of neem is attributed to its bioactive compounds, including azadirachtin, nimbin, and salannin. These compounds disrupt fungal cell membranes, inhibit enzyme activity, prevent spore germination, and generate reactive oxygen species (ROS), leading to fungal cell damage. The study's findings are consistent with those of Obidiegwu *et al.*, (2020) and Uwague,(2019), which also reported the antifungal properties of neem and its ability to reduce yam rot. Moreover, Gwa *et al.* (2018) and Gwa *et al.* (2021) noted significant reductions in yam rot during storage when neem was used, supporting neem's potential as a natural preservative for yam.

The study further confirmed that higher concentrations of neem extract (100%, 75%) exhibited stronger antifungal effects, a finding consistent with previous research by Anukwuorji (2016) and Okigbo *et al* (2015), which showed increased inhibition with higher extract concentrations. Neem extracts were particularly effective against *Fusarium solani*, but slightly less effective against *Aspergillus niger* at lower concentrations (25%, 50%), aligning with earlier reports by Okigbo *et al.* (2015), who also observed varying degrees of inhibition based on concentration.

Phytochemical Analysis of *Azadirachta indica*

A qualitative phytochemical analysis was conducted on the leaf extract of *Azadirachta indica* (neem) to identify the presence of various compounds. The analysis revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, terpenoids, polyphenols, and tannins, while glycosides and coumarins were absent. Alkaloids were detected using both Mayer's and Wagner's reagents, Flavonoids were identified by the alkaline reagent and Shinod's tests, with foam formation confirming their presence. Terpenoids were indicated by a reddish-brown color, while polyphenols and tannins showed a blue-green color. Steroids were also present, indicated by a greenish coloration. The findings align with previous research by Uwague (2019). confirming that neem leaves contain a range of bioactive compounds. These phytochemicals suggest that neem possesses significant medicinal and pharmacological properties.

CONCLUSION

Three fungal species; *Fusarium solani*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Aspergillus flavus*—were found to be responsible for the rotting of yam tubers. The aqueous extract of *Azadirachta indica* (neem) effectively inhibited the growth of these fungi at various concentrations (25%, 50%, 75%, and 100%). The higher concentrations (75% and 100%) were most effective in suppressing fungal growth associated with yam post-harvest rot. Phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of flavonoids, saponins, polyphenols, tannins, and steroids, which may contribute to the antifungal activity of the extract in controlling yam rot.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of the study:

1. Farmers and stakeholders involved in yam production and storage should adopt the use of *Azadirachta indica* (neem) extracts as an eco-friendly and cost-effective method to control post-harvest yam rot caused by fungal pathogens.
2. Concentrations of neem extract at 75% and 100% should be prioritized for use, as these have been shown to be the most effective in inhibiting the growth of *Fusarium solani*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Aspergillus flavus*. Field trials and large-scale application studies should be conducted to validate and refine these concentrations under real-world storage conditions.
3. Given the antifungal properties of neem, promoting the cultivation of neem trees in yam-growing regions could provide an accessible and sustainable source of raw materials for preparing the extracts.
4. Researchers and agricultural product developers should explore the potential for producing neem-based antifungal agents or coatings tailored for post-harvest yam treatment, ensuring ease of use and longer shelf life.
5. Organize training and awareness campaigns to educate farmers about the preparation and application of neem extracts for managing yam rot, emphasizing its benefits over chemical alternatives.
6. Policymakers should support the use of neem extracts through subsidies, research funding, and the development of guidelines for their safe and effective application in agricultural storage.

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